

Documentation Distance Calculations of CellTracker Study

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1. Overview

The script requires following toolboxes and functions. Everything can be found in the “support_functions” folder:

Toolboxes:

- Bio-Formats toolbox to open images (see: <https://docs.openmicroscopy.org/bio-formats/6.1.0/index.html>)

Required functions:

- maxentropic()
- deleteoutside2()

Furthermore, input images should be an 8-bit image and contain 3 channels for each CellTracker color.

The Script is divided into two parts. It contains a first script “Distance_Calculation” for the calculation of distances of all CellTracker labelled pixels within an organoid, and a second script “Analyze_distances” that analyzes and plots the data from the first Script.

The first Script “**Distance_Calculation**” allows one to load an image and interactively select an organoid on it that needs to be analyzed. It calculates all distances in 3 dimensions from the organoid midpoint to all fluorescent “colored” pixels and saves them as a list.

The second script “**Analyze_distances**” creates plots to visualize the overall organoid structure per batch. Results from 3 independent batches are loaded and distances are plotted in various ways such as a histogram with or without a fitted curve and/or normalization. Additionally, mean distance for each channel is calculated and visualized with a barplot.

2. “Distance_Calculation”

This script needs to be run section by section.

1. Define parameters

Define the following 3 parameters:

- zshift is the distance between each slice of the feeded z-stack multiplied by the chromatic aberration 1.47 (RI of Easyindex)
- dimesion: image size
- Outdir: folder where calculated distances should be saved

2. Load image

Image to be loaded needs to be an 8-bit image with 3 channels. Please preprocess image accordingly before using the script.

Figure 1. Example image of CellTracker labelled organoids.

3. Sort Data and preprocess

The 3 channels are separated each image assigned to a core-, a shell- and shell2- channel. Next, any pixel with a pixel value lower than a given threshold is deleted. Threshold is calculated using maxentropy thresholding. Following, every double-positive pixel is assigned to one of the 3 channels by the comparison of their intensities. Double positive pixels describe the pixels that appear on at least 2 of the channels with pixel values unequal to 0. Last, image is binarized.

4. Chose an organoid

Reset organoid number of the organoid to be analyzed by changing the number after “_organoid” in “outpath”.

The script creates a z-stack projection to visualize location of all pixels of the organoid. Here you can encircle the organoid of interest in order to delete everything outside of this circle and create an image containing only the chosen organoid of interest.

Figure 2. Process of interactive selection of a single organoid to analyze.

5. Main calculation

The Main calculation first asses the organoid midpoint by taking the average in x- & y-axis and divide the height of the organoid in z-axis by 2. The distance from this organoid midpoint to every fluorescent-positive pixel is calculated in 3 dimensions and sorted by its color. All distances were normalized by the division of its organoid radius.

In a last section, the calculated distances can be saved and one can return to 4. Section to rename and select the next organoid to be analyzed.

3. “Analyze_distances”

Following parameters need to be defined:

- n = number of batches (=3)
- Dir = path to the folder where all distance results from the first script are
- Totalorg# = number of organoid results from the batches

Next, all distance results are loaded in, via “Dir” + name of the organoid-result-data. After structuring the data, mean distances for each batch and color was calculated. Different histograms and fitted curves for each batch will be added up by all organoids and can be plotted in each section.

*For the publication, calculated mean distances were exported and a barplot was created using GraphPad PRISM. For the histograms, the last section was used to create a normalized histogram of the distance distribution for each color.

Figure 3. Example plots of a fitted curve of all 3 batches, a normalized fitted curve and a histogram of a representative batch.